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The Influence of Values, Beliefs, and Norms on Succession Planning and Organizational Culture: An Investigation of Their Role in Long-Term Success and Survival

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ABSTRACT

Succession planning is a crucial activity within an organizational framework as it facilitates achieving objectives. This process involves identifying individuals who can assume managerial roles within the organization, ensuring that the organization can continue to operate efficiently even in the absence of key personnel due to retirement, resignation, or unfortunate circumstances such as death. Consequently, this study aims to investigate the effect of succession planning and its impact on organizational sustainability by examining evidence from a business organization. To gather data for this study, a combination of questionnaires and personal interviews was employed. Seventy questionnaires were distributed, and fifty completed copies were collected and subsequently organized for analysis. The study primarily focuses on individuals in top and middle-level management positions. The findings of this research demonstrate a significant influence of succession planning on the survival of organizations. Specifically, the results reveal the processes involved in transferring formal knowledge and preserving institutional retention, ultimately contributing to the organization's long-term viability. Moreover, this study underscores the importance of career development in ensuring the organization's existence, particularly in the university setting. Employees perceive career development as a prerequisite for advancement and fulfilling the succession requirements of the organization. Consequently, this emphasis on career development ensures the perpetuity and survival of the institution. In overview, succession planning is vital to organizational success by enabling a seamless transition of managerial responsibilities. The findings of this study highlight the significance of succession planning in organizational sustainability and underscore the positive impact of career development in meeting succession needs. Ultimately, these efforts contribute to the longevity and survival of the institution.

Keywords: Succession planning; Organizational sustainability; Institutional retention; Knowledge; Career development.

1. INTRODUCTION

Succession planning is a deliberate and strategic decision made by organizations to cultivate and nurture the ongoing development of their employees, ensuring stability in critical positions and facilitating the achievement of business objectives (Okwueze & Akanu, 2023).

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An organization's human resource strategy must consider its employees' availability and long-term value to maintain a competitive advantage (Hamadamin & Atan, 2019). Companies with solid organizational structures make a concerted effort to train and develop employees for executive-level positions in advance of any potential leadership gaps that may arise as a result of retirement, sickness, death, or unexpected resignations (Boyd et al., 2015; Mokhber et al., 2017).

Successful succession planning or talent pool management involves the creation of a pipeline or progression of potential leaders throughout the organization's leadership structure. This contrasts replacement planning, focusing solely on identifying backup candidates for specific senior management positions (Garavan et al. 2023). It is essential to consider the retention of key employees and the potential consequences their departure may have on the business (Liu-Lastres et al. 2023). Organizations utilize succession planning to recruit and develop employees who can fill each key role. Successful succession planning involves identifying and recruiting top talent, then training and developing that talent to be ready to take on more responsibilities. According to the available evidence, succession planning is most successful when it begins with defined goals (Jain & Gautam, 2016; Jasir et al. 2023). Rapid incorporation of new technology poses a challenge for measuring and achieving effective performance, as highlighted by Dewi and Fitrio (2022). However, organizations must recognize the importance of their human resources even in the face of modern technology. Rothwell (2001) further suggests that succession planning management ensures the continuity of leadership development to fill expected key positions and foster innovation. He recognizes that a proactive and systematic employee development process yields greater benefits for organizations progressing and navigating the dynamic challenges of a vibrant business environment. Atmaja et al. (2023) argued that succession planning is a control mechanism for dynamic organizations to align human capital needs with business goals.

Continuity planning is crucial for organizations to focus on identifying and developing potential managers or leaders, reducing the need to recruit talent externally (Teng-Calleja et al. 2023). Instead, internal talent development should be the primary focus for organizations in order to cultivate and nurture leaders in the face of attrition. Succession planning is an integral part of the organizational strategic planning process, integrated with developing and implementing the business plan. Hence, progressive organizations ensure that individuals receive appropriate training and developmental opportunities to meet future organizational requirements (Simkhada, 2023). Succession planning aids organizations in formulating strategic business plans and multiple growth strategies while enhancing employees' ability to adapt to the ever-changing environmental demands (Chapman Cook & Karau, 2023).

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The study aims to achieve its objectives by using questionnaires and in-person interviews. The primary focus of this research is to investigate a specific firm and analyze the impact of succession planning on the organization's ability to sustain and grow. Furthermore, the study seeks to examine the significance of succession planning and cultural norms in ensuring the long-term viability and success of the organization. Finally, the transmission and preservation of formal knowledge in institutional retention, crucial factors for organizational longevity, will be assessed through this research. Moreover, this study intends to assess the effectiveness of the University's career development programs in meeting the organization's succession requirements. Additionally, it aims to demonstrate how succession planning can contribute to the prosperity and expansion of businesses. Ultimately, the study's findings will provide valuable insights for developing guidelines to ensure the long-term viability of institutional frameworks.

1.3. Research Questions

These are the study's research questions:

- I. What succession planning approaches are utilized by universities in their succession planning efforts?
- II. How does succession planning impact the ability of universities to sustain operations and facilitate expansion?
- III. What are the processes involved in implementing succession plans within universities?
- IV. What experiences have universities had in developing and implementing succession planning processes?

These research questions aim to investigate the different approaches universities employ in succession planning, analyze the effects of succession planning on universities' ability to operate and grow, understand the implementation processes of succession plans, and gather insights from universities' experiences in developing and executing succession planning initiatives. By addressing these questions, the study will provide valuable information and insights into succession planning within the university context.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The research aims to learn about the building blocks of a successful succession strategy. Succession planning entails preparing persons in advance to take on positions of authority. In his study on leadership succession, Rothwell (2015) highlighted the *Archives of the Social Sciences: A Journal of Collaborative Memory*, 1(1), 67-77 (2023)

significance of thinking forward to future leaders' roles. The primary emphasis of this research is the literature on ensuring the continuity of leadership via succession planning, which is grounded on his previous work. Rothwell uses "important roles" and "critical positions" interchangeably, referring to positions vital for an organization's survival and continuity. Individuals function as leaders within their organizations and possess competencies and unique qualities crucial for organizational effectiveness and success. Leadership permeates the organization, and leaders influence policy by selecting, empowering, training, and developing skills and abilities aligned with organizational objectives. Effective leadership utilizes power to modify and motivate competencies to achieve the organization's mission (Muthimi & Kilika, 2018). In addition, the development of young leaders inside an organization and the leadership development curriculum are all included in leadership succession planning (Vito et al., 2023; Yirci et al., 2023). Finally, it helps leaders and workers feel more connected to the company, which is essential for retaining current and future leaders (Hess et al., 2014; Downs, 2017; McCowan, 2020; Khairy et al., 2023).

This research aims to fill several existing gaps in knowledge. Firstly, it seeks to demonstrate the value of succession planning and its impact on an organization's continued survival and growth. Additionally, it explores how values, beliefs, and conventions influence succession planning and company culture. Furthermore, the effective transfer of formal knowledge and the preservation of institutional retention, both crucial for organizational survival, will be investigated in this research. Moreover, the study can contribute to understanding how career advancement benefits organizations and can be utilized to address succession planning concerns. Lastly, the study's significant contribution lies in providing empirical evidence that succession planning is vital for the ongoing success and expansion of businesses. By implementing succession plans, organizations can ensure smooth operations even after the departure of key employees due to retirement, resignation, or death (Morrow, 2023). This study examines a business organization, focusing on upper and middle management. As a result of this research, businesses can develop succession plans that secure the company's continued existence.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to perform the study methodically and scientifically and achieve valid data and conclusions, the research design is essential. Therefore, an exploratory approach was used for this investigation. With this method, researchers may survey a cross-section of the community they are interested in learning more about and then extrapolate their findings to the whole (Robson, 2002). This study employs an experimental research approach and seeks to gain complete insights into the influence of succession planning on organizational survival and development in the context of the chosen business organization via the collection of both primary and secondary data. There will be 132 participants in this analysis. However, exclusively 50 people were chosen as the study's sample size. The sample included 17 upper-level managers and 33 lower-level managers. Table 1 provides a summary of the sample's demographics.

Table 1: Categories, Population, and Sample Size

Category	Population	Male	Female	Total	Percentage
Top Management	37	11	6	17	34
Middle Management	95	21	12	33	66
Total	132	32	18	50	100

Source: Field Survey

Table 1 details the demographics of the research participants by category, including total population size, gender, total count, and percentage distribution. The research covers two levels of management: upper and lower. The Top Management division has 37 individuals, 11 males and six females. There are 95 people in Middle Management, including 21 males and 12 females. There will be 50 participants in the trial, comprising 32 males and 18 females. The percentages show how many people in each group make up the whole.

3.1 Data Sources

Information needed to answer the study's primary research questions is gathered during the data-collecting phase. For this objective, we evaluated several different approaches and data sets. Data may be divided into two broad types: primary and secondary. Primary data is information gathered mainly for a research project from its source. This information has never been used before and is entirely novel. Depending on the question at hand, researchers might collect primary data via surveys, interviews, observations, or experiments. Secondary data, on the other hand, has already been acquired for another reason by another group of

researchers or an institution. Literature, papers, databases, and historical records are all examples of acceptable data sources. Insights and background for the study may be gleaned from secondary data. Researchers may more successfully achieve their study goals and answer their research questions when combining primary and secondary data. Also, we were able to draw trustworthy conclusions from our research by including both primary and secondary sources in our analysis.

3.2 Population

Employees at the University of Education, Winneba, are the subjects of this research. Senior faculty and staff of the College are represented here. One hundred thirty-two (132) individuals comprise the University's entire staff.

3.3 Sampling Techniques

To compel study subjects, the investigator used a conventional random selection method. Each member of the population has the same chance of being selected using this sampling method. The researcher used this strategy to ensure a balanced sample of workers participated in the study and to reduce the possibility of bias. In addition, a more realistic representation of the University of Education, Winneba staff as a whole may be obtained by this method.

3.4 Data Collection Instruments

Because of the specifics of the information needed for the study, a questionnaire was chosen as the data collection method. With the help of the questionnaire, data collection was made more systematic. In this approach, respondents were sent a set of questions ahead of time and asked to reply using the alternatives or open-ended/closed format given. The questionnaire provided a consistent and systematic approach to obtaining data from a large sample quickly and easily. As a result, the study goals were met, and the influence of succession planning on organizational development and continuity was investigated using a questionnaire used as the research instrument.

3.5 Data Analysis Technique

The study goals were addressed by thoroughly reviewing, classifying, tabulating, and analyzing the acquired data. Both qualitative and quantitative approaches were used in the investigation. However, due to the exploratory character of the study, the researcher relied heavily on a qualitative method for most of the analysis. The replies were analyzed for recurring themes, patterns, and narratives to provide context for the quantitative data. This approach enabled a complete comprehension of the participants' views, experiences, and insights about succession planning and its effect on the development of the company as a whole. The numerical data from the questionnaire replies were also analyzed using quantitative methods. This involved summarizing the data, calculating frequencies, percentages, or other statistical measures to identify trends, relationships, or patterns within the data. Integrating qualitative and quantitative methods in the analysis provided a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the research findings. The emphasis on qualitative analysis allowed for a rich exploration of participants' perceptions and experiences, while quantitative analysis provided statistical support and additional insights to complement the qualitative findings.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Individuals join organizations with specific needs, skills, and expectations, seeking a work environment that allows them to utilize their abilities to fulfill those needs. When organizations can offer such opportunities, it enhances the likelihood of increasing employee commitment. In this study, the researcher investigated the commitment and attitude of employees at the University. The findings regarding employees' commitment and attitude are depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Employee Comments and Attitude (%)

Source: Field survey.

In Figure 1, it can be observed that 23 (22%) of the respondents strongly agree that they actively engage in University activities, while 52 (49%) respondents agree with this statement. On the other hand, 26 (25%) respondents disagree, and 4 (4%) strongly disagree. This result indicates that nearly half of the respondents, which constitute the majority, do not actively involve themselves in the University's activities. This finding aligns with the perspective of Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002), who argue that if management fails to involve employees, their level of participation in organizational activities will be limited, potentially hindering the achievement of succession planning objectives. Figure 2 shows the employee satisfaction with the existing working conditions.

Figure 2: Employee Satisfaction with Working Conditions (%)

Source: Field survey.

In Figure 2, it is evident that 9 (9%) of the respondents strongly agree that they are satisfied with the working conditions at the University. Additionally, 56 (53%) respondents agree with this statement. However, 31 (29%) respondents disagree, and 9 (9%) strongly disagree with being satisfied with the working conditions. This indicates that most employees at the organization are indeed satisfied with the working conditions, which contributes to their ability to perform at their best. When employees are content with their working environment, it can positively impact their motivation and productivity (Elrayah & Sembali, 2023). Figure 3 displays the percentage distribution of respondents' feelings of happiness and comfort with their responsibilities at work. It provides insight into how employees perceive their level of satisfaction and ease in carrying out their job duties.

Figure 3: Employee Happiness and Comfort with Work Responsibilities (%)

Source: Field survey.

In Figure 3, it can be observed that 12 (11%) of the respondents strongly agree that they are satisfied with their responsibilities at work. Furthermore, 75 (71%) respondents agree with this statement. On the other hand, 13 (12%) respondents disagree, and 5 (6%) strongly disagree with being satisfied with their work responsibilities. The findings indicate that most workers expressed satisfaction with the quality of services they provide to their customers. This suggests that employees feel content and fulfilled in carrying out their assigned tasks and responsibilities (Mahmud et al., 2023). Figure 4 illustrates the level of agreement regarding the work environment being conducive for employees. The percentages indicate the distribution of responses among the participants in

the study.

Figure 4: Satisfaction with Conducive Work Environment (%)

Source: Field survey

Figure 4 shows that eight respondents strongly agreed, 70 agreed, 20 disagreed, and seven strongly disagreed, constituting 8%, 67%, 19%, and 6%, respectively. These findings indicate that most respondents expressed comfort and satisfaction with the working environment provided by the organization. The results suggest that the organization has created a conducive work environment promoting employee well-being and productivity (Baquero, 2023). Figure 5 displays the level of satisfaction among respondents regarding monetary benefits.

Figure 5: Satisfaction with Monetary Benefits (%)

Source: Field survey

According to the figure, eight respondents (8%) strongly agreed that they were satisfied with the monetary benefits, 41 respondents (39%) agreed, 36 respondents (34%) disagreed, and 20 respondents (19%) strongly disagreed. The results indicate that a significant portion of the respondents expressed dissatisfaction with the monetary benefits provided by the organization. Most respondents (53%) disagreed or strongly disagreed with their satisfaction with the monetary benefits. This suggests that there is room for improvement in addressing the concerns and expectations of employees regarding their financial rewards within the organization (Presslee et al. 2023).

Figure 6: Effective Tool Usage (%)

Source: Field survey

According to the figure, six respondents (6%) strongly agreed that they have the right tools and equipment to do their job, 63 respondents (60%) agreed, 26 respondents (25%) disagreed, and ten respondents (9%) strongly disagreed. This indicates that most respondents (66%) agreed or strongly agreed that they have access to the necessary tools and equipment to carry out their work effectively. The results suggest that many employees have access to the required tools and equipment, which can contribute to their performance and productivity (Maqsoom et al. 2023). This finding aligns with previous research emphasizing the importance of providing employees with the appropriate working tools to enhance their motivation and improve performance, thereby contributing to the organization's succession planning efforts (Ololade et al., 2023; Huang et al. 2023). Having the right tools and equipment can positively impact employees' ability to fulfill their job responsibilities and play a crucial role in preparing them for future leadership roles within the organization. Figure 7 visually presents the responses regarding whether the employees were consulted when changes were about to take place at the organization.

Figure 7: Consultation of Updating Work Conditions

Source: Field survey

According to the figure, six respondents (6%) strongly agreed that they were consulted during organizational changes, 24 respondents (23%) agreed, 45 respondents (43%) disagreed, and 30 respondents (28%) strongly disagreed. This indicates that most employees (71%) expressed needing to be adequately consulted when management implemented organizational changes. However, the results suggest that most employees need more involvement and participation in decision-making processes during organizational changes. This finding implies that the employees' voices and perspectives must be more effectively considered, resulting in reduced support and contribution to the success of the change initiatives (Bhat et al. 2023). Changes implemented without employee consultation and involvement are less likely to be supported by the employees (Aselage & Eisenberger, 2003; González-González et al. 2023). In order to enhance employee commitment and engagement during periods of change, management must prioritize effective communication, consultation, and involvement of employees (Barach et al. 2024). By actively involving employees in decision-making and providing opportunities for their input, organizations can foster a sense of ownership

and alignment, leading to increased support and successful implementation of changes (Bushe & Lewis, 2023).

This study's discussion section emphasizes many key results with regard to staff participation and satisfaction at the University. Half of the respondents are not actively participating in University activities, which might be a problem for succession planning. This fits well with the findings of other studies that highlight the value of including workers in organizational activities as a means of increasing their involvement and engagement in their work. However, most workers are pleased with their roles and responsibilities as well as the overall atmosphere at their workplace. However, many respondents were unhappy with the financial incentives provided by the company, which may have consequences for both retention and future leadership development. The findings also reveal that many respondents felt they were not consulted prior to organizational changes, which may have dampened their enthusiasm for the initiative. Previous studies have shown that when workers have input into the decision-making process and see changes as within their control, they are more inclined to support them (Vanderfaillie et al., 2023; Manoharan et al. 2023). There are a number of major implications for the University's management and succession planning strategies based on the results of this research. Management should take into account including workers in decision-making processes and offering suitable monetary advantages in order to increase employee participation and engagement (Dako-Gyeke et al., 2023; Al-Zoubi et al. 2023). The University also has to provide a pleasant workplace for its staff and make sure they have all they need to do their jobs well (Casimiro-Andújar et al. 2023). Additional elements that may influence employee participation and pleasure in the workplace are also worthy of investigation in future studies (Asghar, 2023).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study's conclusions hold significant implications for policymakers concerned with organizations' long-term viability and development. It is recommended that companies prioritize succession planning to mitigate any disruptions caused by sudden leadership changes. Establishing systematic processes for identifying and developing potential successors becomes crucial in ensuring a smooth knowledge transfer when key personnel retire. The research highlights the importance of fostering a knowledge-sharing culture and career advancement within organizations. This involves providing employees with structured training and development opportunities to support their professional growth in the medium term. In addition, businesses need to recognize that career advancement and succession planning require ongoing commitment, dedicated resources, and continuous attention. By actively seeking and preparing potential successors, organizations can ensure a sustainable pipeline of capable leaders for the future. In addition, encouraging professional growth across all employees contributes to building a talent pool that can effectively meet future leadership needs. In summary, policymakers should take note of the study's findings and implement measures to prioritize succession planning, facilitate knowledge sharing, and promote career advancement within organizations. By doing so, businesses can enhance their long-term viability, adapt to leadership changes, and nurture a skilled workforce capable of driving continued success.

The research includes significant limitations that need to be taken into account, though. To begin, the research only looks at one firm, which may reduce the broader applicability of the results. Second, data from surveys and interviews are self-reported, which might introduce bias in the results. Third, other tiers of workers aren't included in the research except for upper and middle management. Fourth, the research does not take into account other elements that may affect organizational performance in addition to succession planning's effect on the continuation and expansion of the business.

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1. To make the results more generalizable, future studies might use a bigger sample size that covers numerous businesses.
2. Different data-collecting procedures might be used in future research to lessen response bias.
3. Entry-level workers might be included in future studies on succession planning's effects.
4. Leadership, organizational culture, and external environmental variables are only some of the potential predictors of organizational performance that might be investigated in further research.
5. Further study might examine the efficacy of various succession planning techniques in ensuring the continued existence and expansion of existing businesses.

Ethical approval

Not Applicable.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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